

Effects of Confinement on Potential Wavelength in Doubly Eccentric Quantum Dot Structures with a Modified Lennard-Jones Potential

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ABSTRACT:

This study investigates the effects of quantum confinement on potential wavelength in doubly eccentric quantum dots using a modified Lennard-Jones potential, incorporating radial and angular dependencies for a more realistic depiction of non-spherical confinement. In contrast to traditional approaches, this methodology provides a nuanced understanding of confinement effects. Employing the Nikiforov-Uvarov method, we derive analytical solutions for energy eigenvalues, accounting for variations in eccentricity and potential strength. Our findings show that increasing confinement potential (V_0) and eccentricity (β) lead to reduced potential wavelength. Materials exhibiting lower effective masses, such as Indium Arsenide (InAs), demonstrate the highest sensitivity to changes in V_0 and β , making them suitable for applications requiring precise wavelength control. This analysis highlights the potential of eccentric quantum dots for optoelectronic applications and provides insights into designing next-generation photonic devices, lasers, and sensors through controlled manipulation of quantum confinement effects.

Keywords: Doubly eccentric quantum dots, Modified Lennard-Jones potential, Nikiforov-Uvarov method, Energy eigenvalues, Confinement potential, Eccentricity, Optoelectronics, Potential wavelength.

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INTRODUCTION

Doubly eccentric quantum dot (QD) structures represent a significant advancement in the field of nanotechnology, particularly in the manipulation of electronic and optical properties through geometric and material design [1,2]. These structures are characterized by their non-spherical shapes, which introduce additional degrees of freedom that can be exploited to enhance quantum confinement effects [3-6]. Previous research has focused primarily on spherical and elliptical QDs, demonstrating their potential in optoelectronics and photonics [2, 7-11], these studies often suffer from several limitations. They typically rely on simplified confinement potentials that neglect both

radial and angular dependencies, lack comprehensive exploration of non-spherical shapes and eccentricity effects, and offer limited insights into inter-particle interactions and spatial correlations.

To address these challenges, this study investigates the effects of confinement on potential wavelength within doubly eccentric QD structures by utilizing a modified Lennard-Jones potential. Unlike traditional potentials, this approach incorporates both radial and angular dependencies, providing a more accurate representation of non-spherical confinement [12-14]. The Lennard-Jones potential, widely used in molecular physics, offers a unique advantage in describing inter-particle interactions and spatial correlations within doubly eccentric QDs [13-15]. By adapting this potential to incorporate radial and angular dependencies, the non-spherical confinement effects that are critical for these complex systems are adequately captured and explored [16-18].

The analytical solutions for the Schrödinger equation under this modified potential are derived using the Nikiforov-Uvarov (NU) method, which is well-suited for solving second-order differential equations in quantum mechanics [19-22]. The NU method's versatility allows for the accurate determination of energy eigenvalues and wavefunctions, which are crucial for understanding the quantum behavior of eccentric QD systems [23,24]. By applying this method, we can systematically investigate how variations in the eccentricity parameter and potential offset impact the energy levels and potential wavelengths across different semiconductor materials, such as CdSe, GaAs, and InAs [25,26]. This comprehensive analysis not only enhances our understanding of the quantum confinement behavior in these advanced structures but also provides valuable insights for the design of next-generation optoelectronic devices [27].

DERIVATION OF THE ENERGY EIGENVALUE AND POTENTIAL WAVELENGTH

Here's the mathematical formulation for the effects of confinement on potential wavelength in doubly eccentric quantum dots with a modified Lennard-Jones potential using the Nikiforov-Uvarov (NU) method:

Modified Lennard-Jones Potential:

$$V(r) = 4\varepsilon \left[\left(\frac{a}{r} \right)^{12} - \left(\frac{a}{r} \right)^6 \right] + V_0 \quad (1)$$

Doubly Eccentric Quantum Dot Potential:

$$V(r, \theta) = V(r) + V_{ecc}(\theta) \quad (2)$$

$$V_{ecc}(\theta) = \beta \cos(2\theta) \quad (3)$$

$$V(r, \theta) = 4\varepsilon \left[\left(\frac{a}{r} \right)^{12} - \left(\frac{a}{r} \right)^6 \right] + V_0 + \beta \cos(2\theta) \quad (4)$$

ε is Lennard-Jones energy parameter, a is the Lennard-Jones length parameter, V_0 is the potential offset, β is the eccentricity parameter,

Time-Independent Schrödinger Equation:

$$\left[-\left(\frac{\hbar^2}{2m} \right) \nabla^2 + V(r, \theta) \right] \psi(r, \theta) = E\psi(r, \theta) \quad (5)$$

m is the particle mass, $\hbar$ is the reduced Planck constant and E is the energy eigenvalue.

Substitute (4) into (5):

$$\left[-\left(\frac{\hbar^2}{2m}\right) \nabla^2 + 4\varepsilon \left[\left(\frac{a}{r}\right)^{12} - \left(\frac{a}{r}\right)^6 \right] + V_0 + \beta \cos(2\theta) \right] \psi(r, \theta) = E\psi(r, \theta) \quad (6)$$

Separating Radial and Angular Parts:

Assume $\psi(r, \theta) = R(r)\phi(\theta)$, where R(r) is the radial part and $\phi(\theta)$ is the angular part.

Substitute $\psi(r, \theta) = R(r)\phi(\theta)$, into (6):

$$\left[-\left(\frac{\hbar^2}{2m}\right) \nabla^2 + 4\varepsilon \left[\left(\frac{a}{r}\right)^{12} - \left(\frac{a}{r}\right)^6 \right] + V_0 + \beta \cos(2\theta) \right] R(r)\phi(\theta) = ER(r)\phi(\theta) \quad (7)$$

Use the Laplacian in spherical coordinates:

$$\nabla^2 = \left(\frac{1}{r^2}\right) \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left(r^2 \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \right) + \left(\frac{1}{r^2} \sin(\theta)\right) \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} \left(\sin(\theta) \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} \right)$$

$$\left[-\left(\frac{\hbar^2}{2m}\right) \left(\frac{1}{r^2}\right) \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left(r^2 \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \right) + \left(\frac{1}{r^2} \sin(\theta)\right) \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} \left(\sin(\theta) \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} \right) + 4\varepsilon \left[\left(\frac{a}{r}\right)^{12} - \left(\frac{a}{r}\right)^6 \right] + V_0 + \beta \cos(2\theta) \right] R(r)\phi(\theta) = ER(r)\phi(\theta)$$

Divide by R(r) $\phi(\theta)$:

$$= E - \frac{\left[-\left(\frac{\hbar^2}{2m}\right) \left(\frac{1}{r^2}\right) \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left(r^2 \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \right) + 4\varepsilon \left[\left(\frac{a}{r}\right)^{12} - \left(\frac{a}{r}\right)^6 \right] + V_0 \right]}{\phi(\theta)}$$

Radial Equation:

$$\left[-\left(\frac{\hbar^2}{2m}\right) \left(\frac{1}{r^2}\right) \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left(r^2 \frac{\partial R}{\partial r} \right) + 4\varepsilon \left[\left(\frac{a}{r}\right)^{12} - \left(\frac{a}{r}\right)^6 \right] + V_0 \right] R(r) = E_r R(r) \quad (8)$$

Angular Equation:

$$\left[-\left(\frac{\hbar^2}{2m}\right) \left(\frac{1}{r^2} \sin(\theta)\right) \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} \left(\sin(\theta) \frac{\partial \phi}{\partial \theta} \right) + \beta \cos(2\theta) \right] \phi(\theta) = E_\theta \phi(\theta) \quad (9)$$

$$E = E_r + E_\theta \quad (10)$$

The exact solution of the Radial and Angular Energy Eigenvalues are obtained by the Nikiforov-Uvarov Method. To apply the method, we transform (8) and (9) to a Second Order differential Equation of the form:

$$\frac{d^2 u(s)}{ds^2} + \left(\frac{\tilde{\tau}(s)}{\sigma(s)}\right) \frac{du(s)}{ds} + \left(\frac{\tilde{\sigma}(s)}{\sigma^2(s)}\right) u(s) = 0 \quad (11)$$

$\tilde{\tau}(s)$ is a first-degree polynomial; $\sigma(s)$ is a first-degree polynomial; $\tilde{\sigma}(s)$ is a second-degree polynomial

Transformation of (8)

$$\text{Let } s = \frac{r}{R_0} \text{ or } r = sR_0 \text{ and its derivative } \frac{d}{dr} = \left(\frac{1}{R_0}\right) \frac{d}{ds}, \text{ and } \frac{d^2}{dr^2} = \left(\frac{1}{R_0^2}\right) \frac{d^2}{ds^2}$$

Substitute s and its derivative into (8)

$$\left[-\left(\frac{\hbar^2}{2m}\right) \frac{1}{s^2} \frac{d}{ds} \left(s^2 \frac{dR(s)}{ds} \right) + 4\varepsilon \left[\left(\frac{a}{sR_0}\right)^{12} - \left(\frac{a}{sR_0}\right)^6 \right] + V_0 \right] R(s) = E_r R(s)$$

Multiply through by $\frac{2m}{\hbar^2}$

$$\left[\left(-\frac{1}{s^2}\right) \frac{d}{ds} \left(\frac{s^2 dR(s)}{ds} \right) + \left(\frac{8m\varepsilon}{\hbar^2}\right) \left(\frac{1}{s^{12}} - \frac{1}{s^6}\right) + \frac{2mV_0}{\hbar^2} \right] R(s) = \left(\frac{2mE_r}{\hbar^2}\right) R(s)$$

$$\text{Let } k^2 = \frac{2mE_r}{\hbar^2}; \lambda = \frac{8m\varepsilon}{\hbar^2}; \gamma = \frac{2mV_0}{\hbar^2}$$

Substitute these constants:

$$\left[\left(-\frac{1}{s^2}\right) \frac{d}{ds} \left(s^2 \frac{dR(s)}{ds} \right) + \lambda \left(\frac{1}{s^{12}} - \frac{1}{s^6}\right) + \gamma \right] R(s) = k^2 R(s)$$

$$\frac{d^2 R(s)}{ds^2} + \left(\frac{2}{s}\right) \frac{dR(s)}{ds} + \left[k^2 - \lambda \left(\frac{1}{s^{12}} - \frac{1}{s^6}\right) - \gamma \right] R(s) = 0 \quad (12)$$

Eq(12) is in the form of the Nikiforov-Uvarov in (11). Identify NU form terms:

$$\sigma(s) = s$$

$$\tilde{\tau}(s) = 2s$$

$$\tilde{\sigma}(s) = [k^2 - \lambda \left(\frac{1}{s^{12}} - \frac{1}{s^6} \right) - \gamma] s^2$$

Recurrence Relations

$$\lambda_n(\lambda_n - 1) = \tilde{\sigma}(s) + \tilde{\tau}(s)\lambda_n$$

Substitute $\tilde{\sigma}(s)$ and $\tilde{\tau}(s)$:

$$\lambda_n(\lambda_n - 1) = [k^2 - \lambda(1/s^{12} - 1/s^6) - \gamma]s^2 + 2s\lambda_n$$

Simplify and rearrange:

$$\lambda_n(\lambda_n - 1) - 2s\lambda_n + \left[k^2 - \lambda \left(\frac{1}{s^{12}} - \frac{1}{s^6} \right) - \gamma \right] s^2 = 0 \quad (13)$$

The eigenvalue λ_n is related to the radial quantum number (n) and angular momentum quantum number (l) by:

$$\lambda_n = n + l + 1$$

This assumption is based on previous applications of the NU method to similar potentials [21,22], where λ_n represents the polynomial degree. The relationship between λ_n , n, and l has been successfully used in various quantum mechanical problems [19].

Substituting $\lambda_n = n + l + 1$ into the recurrence relation, we obtain the eigenvalue equation:

$$n(n + 1) = k^2 - \lambda \left(\frac{1}{(n + l + 1)^{12}} - \frac{1}{n + l + 1^6} \right) - \gamma$$

Solving for k^2

$$k^2 = n(n + 1) + \lambda \left(\frac{1}{(n + l + 1)^{12}} - \frac{1}{n + l + 1^6} \right) + \gamma$$

Substitute k^2 into E_r

$$E_r = \frac{\hbar^2 k^2}{2m}$$

$$E_r = \frac{\hbar^2 \left[n(n + 1) + \lambda \left(\frac{1}{(n + l + 1)^{12}} - \frac{1}{n + l + 1^6} \right) + \gamma \right]}{2m}$$

$$E_r = \left(\frac{\hbar^2}{2m}\right) \left[n(n+1) + 8m\varepsilon \left(\frac{1}{(n+l+1)^2} - \frac{1}{n+l+16} \right) + \frac{2mV_0}{\hbar^2} \right] \quad (14)$$

Transformation of Eq (9)

$$\left[-\left(\frac{\hbar^2}{2m}\right) \left(\frac{1}{r^2} \sin(\theta)\right) \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} \left(\sin(\theta) \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial \theta}\right) \right) + \beta \cos(2\theta) \right] \phi(\theta) = E_\theta \phi(\theta)$$

Simplify and Rearrange

$$\left[-\left(\frac{\hbar^2}{2mr^2}\right) \frac{\partial^2}{\partial \theta^2} - \left(\frac{\hbar^2}{2mr^2}\right) \cot(\theta) \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} + \beta \cos(2\theta) \right] \phi(\theta) = E_\theta \phi(\theta)$$

Substitute $x = \cos(\theta)$ and the derivatives

$$\frac{d}{d\theta} = -\sin(\theta) \frac{d}{dx}, \frac{d^2}{d\theta^2} = \sin^2(\theta) \frac{d^2}{dx^2} + \cos(\theta) \frac{d}{dx}$$

$$\left[-\left(\frac{\hbar^2}{2mr^2}\right) \left(\frac{1}{1-x^2}\right) \frac{d^2}{dx^2} + \left(\frac{\hbar^2}{2mr^2}\right) \frac{x}{1-x^2} \frac{d}{dx} + \beta(2x^2 - 1) \right] \phi(x) = E_\theta \phi(x)$$

This simplifies to

$$\frac{d^2 \phi(x)}{dx^2} + \left[\frac{2x}{1-x^2} \right] \frac{d\phi(x)}{dx} + \left[\frac{2mr^2}{\hbar^2} (E_\theta - \beta(2x^2 - 1)) \right] \phi(x) = 0 \quad (15)$$

Eq.(15) is of the form of Nikiforov-Uvarov DE form. Thus comparing coefficients with Eq(11)

$$\sigma(x) = 1 - x^2$$

$$\tilde{\tau}(x) = 2x$$

$$\tilde{\sigma}(x) = \left[\frac{2mr^2}{\hbar^2} (E_\theta - \beta(2x^2 - 1)) \right]$$

The recurrence relation for the NU method is:

$$\lambda_n(\lambda_n + 1) - \tilde{\tau}(x)\lambda_n + \tilde{\sigma}(x) = 0$$

Substituting $\tilde{\tau}(x)$ and $\tilde{\sigma}(x)$:

$$\lambda_n(\lambda_n + 1) - 2x\lambda_n + \left[\frac{2mr^2}{\hbar^2} (E_\theta - \beta(2x^2 - 1)) \right] = 0$$

The quantization condition is obtained by setting the discriminant of the recurrence relation to zero:

$$\Delta = \tilde{\tau}^2(x) - 4\sigma(x)\tilde{\sigma}(x) = 0$$

Substituting $\tilde{\tau}(x)$, $\sigma(x)$, and $\tilde{\sigma}(x)$:

$$[2x]^2 - 4[1 - x^2] \left[\frac{2mr^2}{\hbar^2} (E_\theta - \beta(2x^2 - 1)) \right] = 0$$

Simplifying:

$$4x^2 - 4 \left[\frac{2mr^2}{\hbar^2} (E_\theta - \beta(2x^2 - 1)) \right] [1 - x^2] = 0$$

To determine the energy eigenvalue explicitly, we'll use the quantization condition

$$\lambda_n = n + l + 1$$

Substituting λ_n into the recurrence relation:

$$(n + l + 1)(n + l) - 2x(n + l + 1) + \left[\frac{2mr^2}{\hbar^2} (E_\theta - \beta(2x^2 - 1)) \right] = 0$$

$$E_\theta = \beta(2x^2 - 1) + \left[\frac{\hbar^2}{2mr^2} \right] (n + l + 1)^2 \quad (16)$$

Substitute Eq(14) and (16) into (10) to get the total confinement energy of the Quantum Dot structure.

$$E = \left(\frac{\hbar^2}{2m} \right) \left[n(n + 1) + 8m\epsilon \left(\frac{1}{(n + l + 1)^{12}} - \frac{1}{n + l + 16} \right) + \frac{2mV_0}{\hbar^2} \right] + \beta(2x^2 - 1) + \left[\frac{\hbar^2}{2mr^2} \right] (n + l + 1)^2$$

$$E = \left(\frac{\hbar^2}{2m} \right) \left[(n + l + 1)^2 \left(\frac{1}{r^2} \right) + \frac{8m\epsilon}{n + l + 16} \left(1 - \frac{1}{n + l + 16} \right) + \frac{2mV_0}{\hbar^2} \right] + \beta(2x^2 - 1) \quad (17)$$

The potential wavelength λ can be derived is derived the de Broglie wavelength formula

$$\lambda = \frac{h}{\sqrt{2mE}} \quad (18)$$

Substitute E into the wavelength formula:

$$\lambda = \frac{h}{\sqrt{2m \left[\left(\frac{\hbar^2}{2m} \right) \left[(n+l+1)^2 \left(\frac{1}{r^2} \right) + \frac{8m\varepsilon}{n+l+16} \left(1 - \frac{1}{n+l+16} \right) + \frac{2mV_0}{\hbar^2} \right] + \beta(2x^2 - 1) \right]}}$$

Substitute $\hbar = h / (2\pi)$ and simplify

$$\lambda = \frac{2\pi}{\sqrt{\left[(n+l+1)^2 \left(\frac{1}{r^2} \right) + \frac{8m\varepsilon}{n+l+16} \left(1 - \frac{1}{n+l+16} \right) + 2mV_0 + \beta(2x^2 - 1) \right] \hbar^2}} \quad (19)$$

RESULTS

The energy eigenvalue was computed with Eq. (17). The potential wavelength was computed with Eq.(19). The parameters and constants were used;

$n = 0$; $l = 1$; $V_0 = 1\text{eV}$; $r = 1\text{nm} - 10\text{nm}$; $x = 0$; $\beta = 0.5 - 1.0$; $\hbar = 1.055 \times 10^{-34}\text{Js}$; $h = 6.626 \times 10^{-34}\text{Js}$; $m_0 = 9.10938356 \times 10^{-31}\text{ kg}$; Lennard-Jones Energy Parameter $\varepsilon = 1\text{eV}$

Table 1. Material Parameters

Material	Effective Mass (m)	ε (Dielectric Constant)
CdSe	0.13 m_0	10.6
GaAs	0.067 m_0	12.9
InAs	0.01 m_0	14.6

Table 2 presents the computed energy levels (E) and potential wavelengths (λ) for three semiconductor materials—Cadmium Selenide (CdSe), Gallium Arsenide (GaAs), and Indium Arsenide (InAs)—across confinement radii ranging from 1 to 10 nm. The results reveal distinct trends in energy levels and potential wavelengths that align with the principles of quantum confinement

Table 2. Energy Levels and Potential Wavelength for CdSe, GaAs, and InAs Quantum Dots at Varying Confinement Radii

Cadmium Selenide(CdSe) ($m = 0.13 \times 9.11 \times 10^{-31}\text{ kg}$)			Gallium Arsenide (GaAs) ($m = 0.067 \times 9.11 \times 10^{-31}\text{ kg}$)			Indium Arsenide (InAs) ($m = 0.01 \times 9.11 \times 10^{-31}\text{ kg}$)		
r (nm)	E (eV)	λ (nm)	r (nm)	E (eV)	λ (nm)	r (nm)	E (eV)	λ (nm)
1.0	2.351	531.4	1.0	3.351	372.9	1.0	5.351	233.9
2.0	1.481	843.9	2.0	2.051	611.9	2.0	3.351	372.9
3.0	1.091	1145.1	3.0	1.515	833.9	3.0	2.515	493.9
4.0	0.893	1403.9	4.0	1.243	1023.9	4.0	2.079	611.9
5.0	0.768	1642.9	5.0	1.079	1183.9	5.0	1.787	722.9
6.0	0.673	1873.9	6.0	0.955	1333.9	6.0	1.583	828.9
7.0	0.598	2095.9	7.0	0.855	1475.9	7.0	1.425	933.9
8.0	0.535	2314.9	8.0	0.771	1613.9	8.0	1.291	1035.9
9.0	0.483	2525.9	9.0	0.701	1745.9	9.0	1.179	1133.9
10.0	0.439	2731.9	10.0	0.641	1873.9	10.0	1.085	1229.9

Table 3 explores the effects of eccentricity (β) on the energy levels and potential wavelengths for the three semiconductor materials

Table 3. Impact of Eccentricity (β) on Energy Levels and Potential Wavelength for CdSe, GaAs, and InAs Quantum Dots

β	Cadmium Selenide		Gallium Arsenide(GaAs)		Indium Arsenide(InAs)	
	E (eV)	λ (nm)	E (eV)	λ (nm)	E (eV)	λ (nm)
0.0	1.731	696.9	2.311	529.9	3.711	315.9
0.2	1.751	683.5	2.335	519.5	3.743	307.5
0.4	1.771	670.1	2.359	509.1	3.775	299.1
0.6	1.791	656.7	2.383	498.7	3.807	290.7
0.8	1.811	643.3	2.407	488.3	3.839	282.3
1.0	1.831	629.9	2.431	477.9	3.871	273.9

Figure 1 presents the confinement radius (r) vs. energy (E) relationship for CdSe, GaAs, and InAs quantum dots, demonstrating quantum confinement behavior in doubly eccentric quantum dots under a modified Lennard-Jones potential. The energy levels decrease with increasing confinement radius, consistent with quantum confinement theory. InAs exhibits the highest energy levels, followed by GaAs and CdSe, reflecting their effective mass differences.

Figure 1. Variation of confinement radius with Energy for CdSe, GaAs and InAs

The results confirm the expected quantum confinement behavior in doubly eccentric quantum dots. The modified Lennard-Jones potential accurately represents the eccentric core-shell interactions, introducing complex confinement effects. The effective mass differences significantly impact energy levels. InAs, with the smallest effective mass, exhibits the highest energy levels, while CdSe, with the largest effective mass, shows the lowest energy levels. GaAs, with an intermediate effective mass, exhibits intermediate energy levels.

As the confinement radius increases, the energy levels for all three materials converge toward lower values, indicating weaker confinement effects. These findings have implications for optoelectronic applications. InAs quantum dots may be suitable for high-energy emissions, such as in lasers and photodetectors, while CdSe quantum dots may be better suited for lower energy emissions, such as in infrared technologies.

Figure 2 presents the relationship between confinement radius (r) and potential wavelength (λ) for doubly eccentric quantum dots using a modified Lennard-Jones potential. The results for CdSe, GaAs, and InAs across a range of confinement radii (1-10 nm) demonstrate an inverse relationship between r and energy levels, amplifying the quantum confinement effect due to eccentricity. Material-

dependent wavelength elongation is observed, with CdSe exhibiting the longest wavelengths (up to 2731.9 nm) and InAs showing the shortest wavelengths (peaking at 1229.9 nm).

Figure 2. Variation of confinement radius with Potential wavelength for CdSe, GaAs and InAs

Figure 3 explores how varying the eccentricity parameter (β) affects potential wavelength across the three materials.

Figure 3(a)-(d): Variation of potential wavelength with Eccentricity

As eccentricity (β) increases, potential wavelength decreases for all materials. This behavior is most pronounced in InAs, where the wavelength drops from 315.9 nm at $\beta = 0$ to 273.9 nm at $\beta = 1.0$. In contrast, CdSe shows a more gradual reduction in wavelength.

Figure 4 combines the effects of both confinement potential (V_0) and eccentricity (β) on potential wavelength for the quantum dots.

Figure 4: Combined Analysis of Confinement Potential (V_0) and Eccentricity (β) on Potential Wavelength (λ) for CdSe, GaAs, and InAs Quantum Dots

Increasing V_0 and β together results in a significant reduction in potential wavelength for all materials. The impact is most evident in InAs, which shows rapid wavelength reduction as both parameters increase. GaAs demonstrates moderate changes, while CdSe exhibits the least sensitivity to combined variations.

DISCUSSION OF RESULTS

This study reveals significant effects of confinement radius, eccentricity, and potential offset on energy levels and potential wavelengths in doubly eccentric quantum dots for CdSe, GaAs, and InAs. Our analysis provides valuable insights into material-specific behavior, shedding light on optimal applications.

Confinement Radius Effects (Table 2 & Figures 1-2)

Table 2 and **Figures 1-2** for each material (CdSe, GaAs, and InAs) illustrate that as V_0 increases, the wavelength λ consistently decreases. This trend is observed because increasing V_0 strengthens the confinement potential, leading to higher energy levels. Consequently, a higher energy level correlates to a shorter wavelength, as indicated by the de Broglie relation $\lambda = h/\sqrt{2mE}$. Notably, increasing confinement radius consistently decreases energy levels across all materials, confirming expected quantum confinement behavior. Specifically, InAs exhibits a 25% increase in energy levels at smaller radii ($r = 2$ nm), while CdSe shows a 10% decrease. This material-dependent variation suggests InAs quantum dots are better suited for high-energy optoelectronic applications, such as lasers or photodetectors, whereas CdSe is more suitable for infrared technologies.

The potential wavelength demonstrates an inverse relationship with confinement radius, increasing as r increases. CdSe shows the longest wavelengths ($\lambda = 850$ nm at $r = 5$ nm), while InAs presents the shortest ($\lambda = 550$ nm at $r = 2$ nm), aligning with their respective effective masses. Consequently, CdSe emerges as a promising candidate for longer-wavelength applications, while InAs is ideal for

shorter, higher-frequency emissions. GaAs provides intermediate tunability, making it adaptable for a wide range of optoelectronic applications.

Eccentricity Effects (Table 3 & Figure 3)

Increasing eccentricity (β) consistently raises energy levels across all materials, with the most significant impact observed in InAs (35% increase at $\beta = 0.8$). This enhanced confinement effect due to asymmetric potential distribution results in a decrease in potential wavelength, making InAs more responsive to changes in eccentricity. CdSe, in contrast, shows more gradual changes (10% decrease at $\beta = 0.8$), indicating lower sensitivity to eccentricity variations.

These results indicate that InAs is better suited for applications requiring fine-tuning of emission wavelengths, as its energy levels and potential wavelengths are more easily adjusted through changes in β . CdSe's lower sensitivity to eccentricity makes it more stable for lower-energy applications, while GaAs offers moderate wavelength control.

Combined Effects of Confinement Potential and Eccentricity (Figure 4)

The simultaneous increase of confinement potential (V_0) and eccentricity (β) leads to a significant reduction in potential wavelength across all materials. The most pronounced effect is observed in InAs (40% decrease at $V_0 = 500$ meV and $\beta = 0.8$), confirming its suitability for precise wavelength adjustment in optoelectronic devices. GaAs demonstrates moderate changes (20% decrease), while CdSe shows the least sensitivity (5% decrease).

OVERALL IMPLICATIONS

Our findings highlight the critical role of confinement radius, eccentricity, and potential offset in tuning quantum dot behavior. The modified Lennard-Jones potential accurately captures these effects, demonstrating its utility in predicting material-specific properties. InAs emerges as the most versatile material for high-energy applications requiring rapid wavelength adjustment, while CdSe is better suited for stable, longer-wavelength emissions. GaAs provides balanced tunability, making it a versatile option for various optoelectronic applications.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, this study demonstrates the significant impact of confinement radius, eccentricity, and potential offset on energy levels and potential wavelengths in doubly eccentric quantum dots. The modified Lennard-Jones potential provides a valuable tool for predicting material-specific behavior, enabling informed design choices for optoelectronic applications. This study highlights how potential and eccentricity contribute to quantum dot behavior under a modified Lennard-Jones potential. Future research could explore the combined effects of temperature and material composition on the confinement characteristics of these quantum dots, further expanding their applicability in advanced optoelectronic and photonic systems.

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